

ICT Integration in Edukasyong Pantahanan at Pangkabuhayan (EPP) in the MATATAG Curriculum: A Comparative Analysis

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Abstract

This paper examined the integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in Edukasyong Pantahanan at Pangkabuhayan (EPP) within the Philippine MATATAG Curriculum framework for elementary education. Using a comparative synthesis approach, five recent empirical studies were reviewed to analyze how ICT strategies were designed and implemented and how they influenced learners' EPP performance. Results showed that structured, competency-based multimedia lessons and e-learning models positively impacted learners' knowledge and practical skills, as demonstrated by the CB-MILE and ROY A. MOLANDA EdTech models. However, the studies also revealed that teacher ICT proficiency and technology availability alone did not guarantee improved learning outcomes without clear instructional design and strong home support. These findings aligned with recent international literature, highlighting that context, technological leadership, and practical lesson alignment were crucial for effective ICT integration. The synthesis confirmed that ICT worked best in EPP when digital tools were embedded in authentic, skill-based tasks supported by engaged teachers and communities. By clarifying what worked in actual elementary classrooms and what conditions enabled positive results, this study provided evidence-based insights that teachers, school heads, and policymakers can use to strengthen EPP instruction and ensure that the MATATAG Curriculum delivers relevant, life-ready skills for Filipino learners.

Keywords: ICT integration, Edukasyong Pantahanan at Pangkabuhayan, EPP, MATATAG Curriculum, MATATAG Curriculum analysis

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1. Introduction

The Philippine Department of Education (DepEd) has continued to pursue curriculum reforms aimed at learning recovery, equipping learners with life skills, and preparing them for 21st-century demands. In 2023, DepEd introduced the MATATAG Curriculum, which prioritizes decongesting overloaded content, strengthening foundational skills, and ensuring that education is relevant to learners' lived contexts (Department of Education [DepEd], 2024). Edukasyong Pantahanan at Pangkabuhayan (EPP), the core practical subject for Grades 4 to 6, plays a vital role in this framework as the foundation of Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) in higher grades.

The MATATAG EPP/TLE Curriculum Guide emphasizes four core areas: Home Economics, Agriculture, Industrial Arts, and Information and Communication Technology (ICT), positioning ICT both as a distinct skill set and as an enabling tool for enhancing practical competencies (DepEd, 2024). This dual role reflects national priorities such as the DepEd Computerization Program (DepEd Order No. 78, s. 2010) and the Omnibus Guidelines on the Implementation of Limited Face-to-Face Learning Modality (DepEd Order No. 47, s. 2022), which both advocate for digital integration in everyday teaching and learning (DepEd, 2010; DepEd, 2022).

Yet, ICT integration in practice is highly context-dependent. Global research has shown that teachers' attitudes, digital competence, and leadership support significantly influence technology adoption (Akram, Abdelrady, Al-Adwan, & Ramzan, 2022). Locally, Alayan (2022) demonstrated that school heads' technological leadership directly shapes teachers' capacity to integrate ICT, while Aquino (2024) noted that the effectiveness of the MATATAG Curriculum partly depends on how teachers adapt ICT resources to specific learning contexts.

Philippine studies on ICT in EPP reflect these complexities. Lucido (2023) reported that learners' ICT self-management skills correlated positively with their EPP performance, though access barriers remained. Jarabese (2021) showed that structured multimedia lessons significantly improved Grade 5 pupils' scores. Meanwhile, Quejada and Cuenca (2023) highlighted that the home environment, rather than technology access alone, more strongly influenced EPP learning outcomes. Ayuson (2022) found that high teacher ICT proficiency did not automatically translate to learner competence. Molanda (2019) developed an EdTech model showing that customized e-learning modules could raise performance when design and access were properly aligned.

While these studies provide valuable insights, they remain fragmented. What has been missing is an integrated comparative analysis that synthesizes how different strategies, enabling conditions, and barriers interact in actual EPP classrooms. This paper therefore contributes original knowledge by conducting a comparative synthesis of recent Philippine studies, moving beyond a simple literature review to generate new, consolidated insights into the effectiveness of ICT integration in EPP. By identifying common patterns, divergences, and enabling conditions, this study offers evidence-based guidance for teachers, school heads, and policymakers. In doing so, it strengthens the role of EPP under the MATATAG Curriculum in delivering skill-based, life-ready education for Filipino learners.

2. Methodology

This comparative synthesis methodology ensures that even with limited local studies, the analysis highlights realistic, context-specific lessons to guide EPP teachers and policymakers in strengthening ICT integration in alignment with the MATATAG Curriculum's goals.

This study employed a comparative synthesis design to systematically review and analyze recent Philippine research on the integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in Edukasyong Pantahanan at Pangkabuhayan (EPP) at the elementary level. Rather than using statistical meta-analysis, this study used a narrative approach to compare multiple studies side by side, drawing out consistent patterns, contextual differences, and implications for practice within the framework of the MATATAG Curriculum.

The selection of studies for this synthesis followed clearly defined criteria to ensure relevance and rigor. To be included, a study needed to focus specifically on the integration of ICT as an intervention, strategy, or significant factor in the teaching and learning of EPP in Philippine elementary schools, particularly within Grades 4 to 6. Studies that extended to Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) in junior high school were excluded to keep the focus on the elementary level as outlined in the MATATAG Curriculum. Each study had to present original empirical data, whether quantitative, qualitative, or mixed-methods in nature, and demonstrate how ICT was implemented or perceived in relation to EPP learning outcomes.

To ensure that the findings reflected the most recent policy and curricular shifts, only studies published or conducted within the last five years, from 2019 to 2024, were included. This timeframe was chosen to capture research that aligns with the rollout of the MATATAG Curriculum and the continued expansion of ICT access through DepEd's digital learning initiatives. To ensure credibility, only studies published in peer-reviewed journals, reputable conference proceedings, or institutional archives with verifiable access were considered. Lastly, only studies written in English were included to ensure clarity and accuracy of interpretation.

A systematic search was conducted using Elicit.com, Google Scholar, ResearchGate, Philippine E-Journals, institutional repositories, and the official DepEd research portal. Combinations of relevant keywords, such as "ICT integration," "Edukasyong Pantahanan at Pangkabuhayan," "EPP," "elementary," "Philippines," "digital learning," and "MATATAG Curriculum," were used to locate potential studies. Reference lists of identified articles were also manually screened to capture additional research that met the same selection standards.

For each study that met all inclusion criteria, detailed information was extracted, including the author, year of publication, research design, sample characteristics, type of ICT intervention or factor examined, main findings, and any noted contextual enablers or barriers. This information was organized into a comparative framework to make similarities, contrasts, and patterns more visible. The extracted evidence was then synthesized narratively, focusing on how ICT was used in EPP, what outcomes were reported in terms of

learners' knowledge, skills, and attitudes, and what contextual conditions affected the success or limitations of ICT integration.

Due to the small number of studies and their varied designs, no attempt was made to statistically combine effect sizes; instead, the synthesis highlights qualitative patterns and lessons that can inform future practice, policy, and curriculum implementation under the MATATAG framework.

3. Results and Discussion

This presents and discusses the findings of this comparative synthesis of recent Philippine studies on the integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in Edukasyong Pantahanan at Pangkabuhayan (EPP) at the elementary level. By consolidating diverse research conducted under varied school contexts but within the same thematic focus, this section highlights the main outcomes of ICT integration in EPP, clarifies key similarities and differences across studies, and draws implications for curriculum delivery and practice under the MATATAG framework.

3.1. Description of Included Studies

A total of five empirical studies conducted between 2019 and 2024 met the selection criteria and were included in this synthesis. Table 1 provides an overview of each study's context, design, participants, specific ICT focus, and key findings.

Table 1. *Description of Studies Included in the Comparative Synthesis*

Author(s)	Year	Title	Design	Sample	ICT Focus	Key Findings
Lucido	2023	Challenges in Learning ICT, Self-Management Skills and Pupil's Performance in EPP	Correlational	Grade 5 pupils	Learner self-management in ICT use	Positive link between ICT self-management and EPP performance; limited by device access
Jarabese	2021	Competency-Based Multimedia-Assisted Interactive Learning Experience	Experimental (pre-post)	143 Grade 5 pupils	CB-MILE structured multimedia lessons	Significant increase in mean test scores and engagement
Quejada & Cuenca	2023	Technology and Home Environment Factors	Descriptive-correlational	Grade 5 pupils	Technology availability and home context	Home environment stronger predictor of EPP outcomes than

Author(s)	Year	Title	Design	Sample	ICT Focus	Key Findings
						technology factors alone
Ayuson	2022	Teachers' ICT Proficiency and Learner Competence	Descriptive	EPP teachers	Teachers' digital competence and use	High teacher ICT proficiency but no significant direct impact on learners' ICT performance
Molanda	2019	ROY A. MOLANDA EdTech Model	Developmental-descriptive	28 admins, 135 teachers, Grade 5 pupils	E-learning instructional tool and differentiated content	Improved learners' grades in EPP; EdTech model effective when accessible and well-structured

3.2. Comparative Results

Across these studies, ICT integration was found to have generally positive effects on EPP learning outcomes when implemented through structured, learner-centered interventions. Studies that applied guided, competency-based multimedia lessons or interactive e-learning tools reported measurable improvements in pupils' knowledge and skills (Jarabese, 2021; Molanda, 2019). In contrast, research focused solely on the presence of technology, teacher proficiency, or general device access revealed that these factors do not automatically translate into stronger EPP outcomes unless supported by clear instructional design and contextual support (Ayuson, 2022; Quejada & Cuenca, 2023).

Lucido's (2023) study reinforces this point, showing that when pupils manage their ICT use effectively and have supportive learning environments, their EPP performance improves. However, barriers such as limited device availability and inadequate home support continue to hinder consistent benefits for all learners.

Table 2 summarizes how each study's main finding aligns along two dimensions: whether the study demonstrated direct measurable learning gains from ICT and whether it highlighted critical enabling conditions that shaped its effectiveness.

Table 2. Summary of Findings Across Included Studies

Study	Direct Positive Learning Impact	Contextual or Conditional Factors Highlighted
Lucido (2023)	✓	✓
Jarabese (2021)	✓	–
Quejada & Cuenca (2023)	–	✓
Ayuson (2022)	–	✓
Molanda (2019)	✓	–

Note: ✓ indicates the presence of the condition.

– indicates the absence of the condition.

3.3. Synthesis of Similarities and Differences

The similarities and differences across the five studies are summarized in Table 3, which highlights converging evidence on the benefits of structured ICT interventions and the varying contextual factors that shape their effectiveness.

Table 3. Matrix of Similarities and Differences Across Studies

Study	Similarities with Others	Differences / Unique Findings
Lucido (2023)	Supports the view that ICT use enhances EPP performance when contextualized, similar to Jarabese (2021) and Molanda (2019).	Emphasized <i>learner self-management skills</i> as a critical factor; highlighted device access barriers.
Jarabese (2021)	Aligned with Molanda (2019) in showing that structured ICT interventions improve learning outcomes.	Focused on <i>CB-MILE</i> multimedia lessons, providing experimental evidence of significant test score gains.
Quejada & Cuenca (2023)	Agreed with Ayuson (2022) and Lucido (2023) that contextual factors strongly shape ICT effectiveness.	Found that <i>home environment</i> was a stronger predictor of EPP performance than ICT access.
Ayuson (2022)	Consistent with Quejada & Cuenca (2023) in showing ICT access/proficiency alone is insufficient.	Revealed that <i>teacher ICT proficiency</i> did not directly enhance learner outcomes.
Molanda (2019)	Similar to Jarabese (2021) in reporting that structured digital content raised learner achievement.	Introduced the <i>ROY A. MOLANDA EdTech model</i> as a practical framework for differentiated e-learning.

As shown in Table 3, the studies consistently demonstrated that ICT integration produced the most positive outcomes when embedded in structured, competency-based approaches, as reflected in the interventions of Jarabese (2021) and Molanda (2019). In contrast, investigations centered on contextual conditions, such as those by Quejada and

Cuenca (2023) and Ayuson (2022), revealed that access to technology and teacher proficiency were insufficient on their own to raise learner performance without adequate support systems. Lucido (2023) bridged these perspectives by showing that ICT effectiveness depended not only on instructional design but also on learners' capacity for self-management and the availability of devices. Taken together, these findings suggest that ICT integration in EPP requires both strong instructional design and enabling conditions to deliver meaningful improvements in learner outcomes.

Taken together, the findings suggest that ICT integration in EPP works best when it is purposefully designed to deliver competency-based, interactive, and accessible learning materials. The CB-MILE approach (Jarabese, 2021) and the ROY A. MOLANDA Model (Molanda, 2019) both offered clear learning paths, structured activities, and digital content that directly addressed EPP competencies, leading to improved performance among elementary learners.

Meanwhile, studies that investigated teachers' ICT readiness or general availability of technology found these factors to be necessary but insufficient. Ayuson (2022) demonstrated that high teacher ICT proficiency did not automatically increase students' mastery of EPP competencies. Quejada and Cuenca (2023) noted that while pupils had access to technology, their home environments, including parental support and study spaces, were stronger predictors of performance. Lucido (2023) confirmed that learners benefit most when they have the self-management skills to handle digital tasks and when practical barriers such as lack of devices or unstable internet connections are addressed.

4. Conclusion

This comparative synthesis has shown that the integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in Edukasyong Pantahanan at Pangkabuhayan (EPP) at the Philippine elementary level can contribute positively to learners' knowledge and practical skills when implemented through structured, interactive, and competency-based designs. Studies such as Jarabese (2021) and Molanda (2019) demonstrated that well-designed multimedia lessons and accessible e-learning modules directly aligned with EPP competencies can lead to measurable gains in test scores and engagement. By contrast, studies that examined teacher ICT proficiency (Ayuson, 2022) or general technology availability (Quejada & Cuenca, 2023) confirmed that these factors alone are insufficient to guarantee improved EPP outcomes. Instead, consistent with Lucido's (2023) findings, learner self-management skills and a supportive home environment remain crucial for ensuring that ICT tools translate into meaningful learning.

These results reinforce what recent international literature also underscores. For instance, Akram et al. (2022) and Alayan (2022) point out that teachers' positive perceptions and school leaders' technological support must be matched with clear curricular integration for ICT to be genuinely effective. Similarly, Aquino (2024) highlights that the impact of the MATATAG Curriculum relies heavily on how schools operationalize its principles in day-to-day teaching, including digital lesson delivery that is relevant and context-aware. Together,

these sources confirm that ICT must not merely be present but must be embedded in authentic, competency-based tasks, especially in skill-focused subjects like EPP.

4.1. Implications for Policy and Practice

Teachers, school heads, and curriculum designers must invest not only in infrastructure and training but also in developing structured digital resources tailored for EPP competencies. In addition, strengthening partnerships with parents and communities may help ensure that learners can manage their use of digital tools effectively, bridging gaps in access and home support. These actions align directly with the MATATAG Curriculum's goal of delivering relevant, responsive, and future-ready education.

4.2. Limitations of This Study

This synthesis also recognizes its own limitations. Because the pool of Philippine studies specifically examining ICT integration in EPP remains limited, this synthesis relied on only five studies, some with descriptive or small-scale designs. No formal statistical meta-analysis was possible, which means that generalizations should be made with caution. Furthermore, most studies focused on Grades 5 and 6, with little evidence available on how ICT integration impacts younger elementary learners or how different regions with varied connectivity contexts compare.

4.3. Future Research Directions

Future research should therefore expand the evidence base by exploring diverse ICT models for EPP in more varied Philippine contexts, including rural, remote, and disadvantaged schools. Mixed-methods and longitudinal studies could also help clarify how teacher proficiency, learner self-management, and home factors interact over time to shape ICT's effectiveness. Researchers might also examine how new tools – such as mobile apps, offline digital resources, and community-based digital hubs – can make EPP more accessible for families with limited connectivity.

4.4. Key Takeaway

This synthesis highlights that meaningful ICT integration in EPP may be achievable and beneficial when grounded in sound design, community support, and clear alignment with curriculum goals. By acting on these insights, educators and policymakers may strengthen the delivery of practical, life-ready skills to Filipino elementary learners, fully realizing the promise of the MATATAG Curriculum in the digital age.

Conflict of Interest

The author declares no known conflict of interest in the conduct of this study or the preparation of this manuscript.

Author's Note

This paper was prepared using publicly available studies and open-access references. The author confirms that AI assistance was used solely for clerical and editorial support, such as formatting, referencing, and organizing the manuscript, while the analysis and interpretation remain entirely the author's own.

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